

CHECKING THE STRENGTH OF REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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Abstract. This article presents a methodology and algorithm for analyzing the tensile and compressive deformations of truss elements made of elastic rods. Numerical results are obtained and analyzed. When static forces are applied to the truss joints, the maximum stresses in the rods are identified.

Keywords: truss, rod, support, reaction force, moment of inertia, cross-sectional area, radius, compression, tension.

Introduction

Today, various metal structures are widely used in the construction industry, including trusses made of metal [1, 2]. In solving such problems, methods of construction mechanics are extensively applied. For this purpose, we use the equilibrium equations known from the statics section of theoretical mechanics [3, 4]. Analyzing truss elements as rods is considered an important issue. Therefore, the ABAQUS software, based on the finite element method, is utilized [5, 6]. This article discusses the problem of calculating the truss. The stresses during compression and tension in each rod are determined, and the conditions under which the strength exceeds the yield limit are examined. The calculations utilize the properties of St3 grade steel.

Let's assume the calculation scheme depicted in Figure 1 is given. We will solve this truss using the ABAQUS software based on the finite element method. As an example, the dimensions of the truss elements are as follows: length $l=4$ m, connected at a 60° angle. A force P is applied at point D. The truss is fixed at point A with a stationary hinge and at point E with a movable hinge. The diagram of the calculation scheme is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Calculation Scheme

We will analyze the equilibrium equations of statics separately for the sections at each joint using methods of construction mechanics. By applying the equilibrium conditions for each node, the following equations are obtained.

Figure 2. Calculation Scheme for Section at Point D.

In this case, the equilibrium equation will be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \uparrow^+ \sum F_y = 0; & \quad -P + F_{DC} \cos 30^\circ = 0 & \quad F_{DC} = \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} P \text{ kN} \\ \leftarrow^+ \sum F_x = 0 & \quad F_{DE} + F_{DC} \cos 60^\circ = 0 & \quad F_{DE} = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} P \text{ kN} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3. Calculation Scheme for Section at Point C.

In this case, the equilibrium equation will be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \uparrow^+ \sum F_y = 0 & \quad F_{CE} \cos 30^\circ - F_{DC} \cos 30^\circ = 0 & \quad F_{CE} = -\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} P \text{ kN} \\ \rightarrow^+ \sum F_x = 0 & \quad F_{DC} \cos 60^\circ - F_{CB} + F_{CE} \cos 60^\circ = 0 & \quad F_{CB} = \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} P \text{ kN} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4. Calculation Scheme for Section at Point B.

In this case, the equilibrium equation will be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \uparrow^+ \sum F_y = 0 \quad & F_{BE} \cos 30^\circ - F_{BA} \cos 30^\circ = 0 \quad & F_{BE} = F_{BA} \\ \rightarrow^+ \sum F_x = 0 \quad & F_{CB} - F_{BE} \cos 60^\circ - F_{BA} \cos 60^\circ = 0 \\ & F_{BE} = -\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} P \text{ kN} \quad & F_{BA} = -\frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} P \text{ kN} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5. Calculation Scheme for Section at point E.

In this case, the equilibrium equation will be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \uparrow^+ \sum F_y = 0 \quad & E_y - F_{BE} \cos 30^\circ - F_{CE} \cos 30^\circ = 0 \quad & E_y = 2P \text{ kN} \\ \rightarrow^+ \sum F_x = 0 \quad & F_{EA} - F_{DE} - F_{CE} \cos 60^\circ + F_{BE} \cos 60^\circ = 0 \quad & F_{EA} = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} P \text{ kN} \end{aligned}$$

The cross-sectional area of the truss rods is $S=30 \text{ cm}^2$, and for St3 grade steel with a yield strength of $\sigma_{oq}=140 \text{ MPa}$, the force required for failure (exceeding the yield limit) is

$$P_{kr} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \sigma_{oq} \cdot S \approx 0,87 \cdot 140 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 30 \cdot 10^{-4} \approx 365 \text{ kN.}$$

Now, the buckling limit for the truss rods during compression will be determined:

$$P_{kr} = \frac{\pi^2 EJ}{4l^2} \quad J = \frac{\pi b h}{64} (h^2 + b^2)$$

(in the problem statement, $h=b$ —diameter ($r \approx 3,1 \text{ sm}$))

$$J \approx 1,45 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^4 - \text{Inertia moment} \quad P_{kr} \approx 4,467 \text{ kN}$$

For the case where $P=8 \text{ kN}$, $S=1 \text{ m}^2$, $E=200 \cdot 10^9$, the solutions obtained using both the analytical method and the ABAQUS software are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{DC} &= 9.24 \text{ kN} \\ F_{DE} &= -4.62 \text{ kN} \\ F_{BE} &= 9.24 \text{ kN} \\ F_{BA} &= 9.24 \text{ kN} \\ E_y &= 16 \text{ kN} \\ F_{EA} &= 4.62 \text{ kN} \\ F_{CE} &= 9.24 \text{ kN} \\ F_{CB} &= 9.24 \text{ kN} \end{aligned}$$

Source 1

Frame: Increment 1: Step Time = 1.000

Loc 1: Integration point values from source 1

Output sorted by column "Element Label".

Field Output reported at integration points for part: FERMA-1

Element Label	Int	S.S11
Pt	@Loc 1	

1	1	9.23760E+03
2	1	-9.23760E+03
3	1	-4.61880E+03
4	1	9.23760E+03
5	1	9.23760E+03
6	1	-9.23760E+03
7	1	-4.61880E+03

Minimum	-9.23760E+03
At Element	6
Int Pt	1
Maximum	9.23760E+03
At Element	5
Int Pt	1
Total	0.

Output sorted by column "Node Label".

Field Output reported at nodes for part: FERMA-1

Node Label	RF.RF1	RF.RF2
@Loc 1	@Loc 1	

1	0.	0.
2	0.	0.
3	0.	16.E+03
4	0.	0.
5	1.81899E-12	-8.E+03

Minimum	0.	-8.E+03
At Node	4	5
Maximum	1.81899E-12	16.E+03
At Node	5	3
Total	1.81899E-12	8.E+03

CONCLUSION

Thus, when a force P is applied, the rods under compression begin to buckle when it reaches $P_{kr} \approx 4,467$ kN, and the rods under tension fail at $P_{kr} \approx 365$ kN. The results obtained using both analytical and numerical methods for the case where an 8 kN force is applied at point D of the truss are presented. The solutions confirm consistency with the results obtained through the analytical method.

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